

Impact Analysis Report

Deliverable 3.2 Impact Analysis

Prepared by: Startup Wise Guys

Description

This report is designed to comprehensively cover all aspects of the acceleration programme for women-led deep tech startups analyzing the impact of the acceleration programme, including the execution, results achieved, feedback collected, and analytical insights into the services provided

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Table 1. Project information

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 Overview of the Acceleration Programme

The EmpoWOMEN project offered a unique six-month Acceleration programme divided into two parts: Part 1 "Build and Scale", led by Startup Wise Guys, and Part 2 "Investment Readiness" led by Business Angels Europe. This programme provided equity-free funding, prizes, and service vouchers to 11 selected women-led companies operating in the deep tech sector. Most of the programme activities were happening online, but it also included three onsite events: the PODIM conference, the SLUSH conference, and Demo Day held onsite in Helsinki.

1.2 Key Findings and Impact Summary

The main impact that we were willing to bring with this programme was to unlock for the female led startup potential from less-mature startup ecosystems from the widening countries to help them to overcome this challenge.

Our main goal was to help startups coming from or operating in Widening-area countries, to train them so that they can be prepared for funding and increase their presence in the deep tech investors' portfolios.

With a help of this Acceleration programme to prepare women-led deep tech startups to be ready for raising additional funding to lower the barriers that women founders and deep tech startups find when trying to develop a market-ready technology which takes longer to take to the market. A connected ecosystem of women founders in deep tech to bring real equal opportunities in the field.

1.3 Recommendations for Future Programmes

One of the key recommendations is that aligning startup maturity levels with tailored content is a win-win approach. Continuous support for women entrepreneurs, encompassing both educational and mental resilience aspects, is crucial for success, particularly in traditionally male-dominated industries. Emphasis should be placed on the idea that a gender barrier has no place in the business world; ideally, success should be driven solely by merit and innovation, irrespective of gender.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and Scope of the Report

This report aims to assess the outcomes and overall impact of the EmpoWOMEN project, a six-month Acceleration programme designed to support women-led deep tech companies across Europe. This report focuses on evaluating the effectiveness of the programme in providing crucial growth resources, such as equity-free funding, mentorship, and access to industry events.

The scope of this analysis includes both the virtual and in-person elements of the programme, highlighting the experiences of 11 selected companies. Key activities included online workshops, networking sessions, and three high-profile onsite events: the PODIM and SLUSH conferences, as well as Demo Day. These events provided significant platforms for participants to connect with potential investors, partners, and experts within the deep tech ecosystem.

Through this report, we aim to identify the strengths and areas for improvement in the programme's design and delivery, offering valuable insights to enhance future initiatives aimed at empowering female entrepreneurs in the tech industry.

2.2 Overview of Women-led Deep Tech Startups in the Programme

Out of 170 applications, 11 of the most progressive women-led companies were selected to participate in this programme. The selection process prioritized factors such as the startups' technological advancements, the strength of their teams, the level of innovation, and overall growth potential.

Leading the cohort is the Health Tech vertical, represented by 5 startups, while the remaining startups span a diverse range of sectors, including Space Tech, Cybersecurity, AgriTech, Renewable Energy, and Media Data Analytics. All participating startups are in the early stages of development, seeking support to transition from prototyping to market-ready products, secure their first sales, and attract investment opportunities.

3. PROGRAMME EXECUTION OVERVIEW

3.1 Objectives and Goals of the Acceleration Programme

The primary objective of the EmpoWOMEN programme was to provide comprehensive support, including equity-free funding, to 11 female founders in deep tech. The goal was to drive significant business growth

while maintaining a minimal dropout rate. This initiative was not only aimed at helping these women-led startups reach their individual milestones but also at strengthening the broader female founder ecosystem by encouraging and inspiring other women entrepreneurs.

Over the six-month programme, participants were required to meet key performance indicators (KPIs) set at the start, with a focus on measurable growth. Participants had the flexibility to select the activities that would best support their business growth, based on their initial stage, product development progress, and specific company goals for the six-month period.

The support provided included tailored programme content, expert mentorship, and coaching sessions, all aimed at helping founders overcome challenges, scale their businesses, and bring their solutions closer to market readiness.

3.2 Programme Structure

Startup Wise Guys (SWG) provided the structure and framework for the six-month EmpoWOMEN programme, which was specifically designed for early-stage female founders and entrepreneurs. The training focused on key components essential for startup growth, including:

- Developing a strong business idea with a clear problem statement and solution.
- Acquiring the first customers.
- Advancing product development from the R&D stage to a Minimum Viable Product (MVP) and prototypes.
- Building a network of like-minded individuals, role models, and mentors.
- Preparing for the first round of investment.

The programme was divided into two parts:

PART 1: "Build and Scale" (led by SWG) – 8 Weeks + Progress Day

This phase focused on helping startups solidify their business foundation and scale their operations. It included:

- **Q&A Sessions** covering weekly topics.
- **Peer-to-Peer Sessions** for knowledge sharing and collaboration.
- **Webinars** on key business and scaling topics.
- **Individual Pitch Training** to refine pitch decks and presentation skills.
- **Fireside Chats with Role Models** to inspire and share practical insights.
- **Progress Day**, where startups presented their progress and received feedback.

PART 2: "Investment Readiness" (led by BAE) – 10 Weeks + Demo Day

- **Webinars** focused on investment readiness and pitching to investors.
- **Dedicated Mentor Day**, where startups received targeted mentorship from industry experts.
- **Demo Day**, the final event where startups showcased their progress to investors and stakeholders.

Programme Timeline for 6 months

FIGURE. 1 Programme Timeline

Important Milestones

Table 3. Programme Important Milestones

Time period	Task	Result	Achievements
Month 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preparation of the KPIs ● PODIM conference attendance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Delivered Goals & KPIs PDF document ● Received 5K EUR grant after its confirmation ● 5k EUR Mentor voucher unlocked ● 5k EUR event voucher unlocked 	All 11 startups
Month 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Report on Part 1 KPIs including sufficient evidence ● Participation in Progress Day 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Received 20k EUR grant after confirmation ● Investment Readiness voucher unlocked 	All 11 startups
Month 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Report on Part 2 KPIs including sufficient evidence ● SLUSH conference attendance ● Demo Day attendance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Received 20k EUR grant after confirmation 	All 11 startups

In addition to the core programme activities, several additional activities were organized throughout the EmpoWOMEN programme to provide ongoing support and opportunities for the startups:

- **On-demand Meetings** with Lead coaches, arranged upon request.
- **Extra Mentoring Sessions** with industry experts.
- **Attendance at Two Major Tech Events** to enhance networking and market exposure.
- **Demo Day** was held as an onsite event in Helsinki, where startups presented their progress to a broader audience.

During Part 1, startups had access to comprehensive learning materials, including:

- **Pre-recorded Videos** on key topics.
- **Numerous Tasks** provided in Word and Excel document templates.
- **Other Resources** to help startups understand each topic and apply the concepts to their own businesses.

The materials were integrated into the Airtable interface, allowing startups to track their progress and apply practical insights to their individual cases. Though no new content was released in Part 2, startups still retained access to the Part 1 materials for continued reference.

Throughout the programme, daily communication took place via Slack communication platform, where Programme Lead was readily available to address any questions or provide ongoing support. All live sessions were conducted via Zoom meeting platform, ensuring seamless interaction between participants and mentors.

3.3 Participant Selection Criteria

After closing the first open call for the EmpoWOMEN programme, the open call management team initiated and managed the evaluation process, ensuring fairness and thoroughness at every stage. This process, which is further detailed in D2.1 Open Call Documents and D2.2 Discovery Impact Report, started with an eligibility check, aimed at confirming whether the applications adhered to the administrative conditions of the programme. Out of the 170 applications received, 46 were found ineligible, leaving 124 submissions to proceed further.

The next stage involved remote evaluation by external experts selected for their technical and business expertise in entrepreneurship, innovation, and investment. Each proposal was independently assessed by two evaluators—one focusing on technical aspects and the other on business considerations—against three key criteria: Excellence, Impact, and Implementation. This phase emphasized the innovation, societal and economic potential, and feasibility of the proposed projects, ensuring a balanced and well-rounded evaluation.

To uphold consistency and fairness in scoring, a normalisation process was applied. This mathematical adjustment corrected for any evaluator biases or distortions, providing an equitable comparison across all applications. The normalised scores determined the ranking of the proposals, with the top 22 projects moving on to the next stage.

These top-ranked applicants participated in online interviews, where external evaluators, alongside a programme consortium partner, delved deeper into the project concepts and team capabilities. This phase aimed to evaluate the startups’ alignment with the programme’s goals while maintaining a transparent and impartial evaluation process. Finally, the combined scores from the remote evaluation and interviews informed the final ranking. The highest-scoring projects were offered sub-grant agreements and invited to join the EmpoWOMEN programme.

3.4 Timeline of Key Activities and Milestones

After closing the first open call for the EmpoWOMEN programme, the open call management team initiated and managed the evaluation process, ensuring fairness and thoroughness at every stage. This process, which is further detailed in D2.1 Open Call Documents and D2.2 Discovery Impact Report, started with an eligibility check, aimed

Table 4. Key activities and milestones

Events & Date	Short Description
<p>Programme start “Welcome session” and onboarding (May 6, 2024)</p>	<p>The programme officially kicked off with an online Welcome Session, attended by 11 selected startups and the project’s partners. The primary goal of the event was to provide an in-depth explanation of the programme structure, expectations, and key milestones. Additionally, this session offered a valuable opportunity to address any outstanding questions from the participants and ensure that everyone was fully onboarded and prepared to begin the journey.</p>
<p>PODIM conference (May 12-14, 2024)</p>	<p>As part of the first event voucher provided by the programme, the participating startups attended the PODIM conference. This event offered them a platform to showcase their innovations to a European and global audience, enhancing their visibility and market presence. In addition to exhibiting their solutions, the startups were included in the PODIM Startup Catalogue, a key resource for investors seeking innovative ventures. This opportunity also allowed them to engage directly with investors and potential customers, fostering meaningful connections and opening doors to future business collaborations.</p>

Events & Date	Short Description
<p>Progress Day (July 10, 2024)</p>	<p>The Progress Day marked an important checkpoint in the EmpoWOMEN programme. This online event brought together all 11 startups, project partners, and lead coaches to review and assess the startups' progress after completing Part 1 of the programme. The session focused on evaluating the achievements, challenges, and key performance indicators (KPIs) met by each startup, providing feedback to help them prepare for the next phase of their journey.</p>
<p>Summer break (July 10, 2024 - September 6, 2024)</p>	<p>Following Progress Day, the programme entered a summer break to allow the startups to recharge and reflect. During this period, no live sessions were scheduled. However, startups were given a summer assignment focused on developing their financial plans and outlining their investment needs. Additionally, startups had the opportunity to continue mentoring sessions during the break, ensuring they remained on track with their goals despite the pause in structured activities.</p>
<p>Start of Part 2 "Investment Readiness" (September 5, 2024)</p>	<p>The second phase of the programme, Investment Readiness, kicked off with an online group session. During this event, the startups were introduced to the key objectives and structure of Part 2. The session outlined what they could expect in terms of support, activities, and milestones as they prepared to attract investment and scale their businesses.</p>
<p>Demo Day (November 19, 2024)</p>	<p>The final event of the programme, Demo Day, served as a graduation ceremony for the 11 participating startups. Each startup delivered a pitch presentation, competing for one of three money prizes awarded to the most promising companies. The event featured participation from all programme partners, external jury members, and potential investors, offering startups a valuable opportunity to showcase their progress and secure additional support.</p>
<p>SLUSH conference (November 20, 21, 2024)</p>	<p>In a similar manner to the first event voucher, the startups attended the Slush event in Helsinki, benefiting from an enhanced platform for networking and exposure. This time, a shared booth provided a central space for the startups to present their innovations collectively, drawing increased attention from attendees. Additionally, all startups actively participated in one-on-one meetings with investors, corporates, and mentors, maximising their opportunities to build strategic connections and gain valuable insights for their growth.</p>

3.5 Mentorship (vouchers)

The mentorship component of the EmpoWOMEN programme was a vital pillar in ensuring the success of the participating startups.

At the outset of the programme, each startup was assigned a Lead Coach. The primary role of the Lead Coach was to support the startup throughout the six-month programme, ensuring that the set KPIs were both reasonable and achievable. Lead Coaches held regular meetings with their assigned startups to discuss critical challenges, provide guidance, and agree on actionable next steps. Their main responsibility was to ensure that the KPIs were met and that the evidence provided was sufficient to demonstrate the startup's progress and achievements.

Each startup had the opportunity to choose up to six mentors during the six-month programme, selecting individuals who best matched their specific needs. A total of 60 individual mentoring sessions were conducted throughout the programme, with an additional 39 one-on-one sessions held on the dedicated Mentor Day. These mentor sessions provided crucial support in helping startups achieve their KPIs and business goals. To assess the effectiveness and impact of these sessions, feedback was collected from both the startups and the mentors, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of the mentorship experience

3.6 Networking events (vouchers)

3.6.1 PODIM Conference

Founded in 1980 and situated in Slovenia, Podim has evolved into the leading and most influential startup and tech event in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE), where innovation converges with business opportunities, capital infusion, knowledge exchange, and expertise. Year after year, it serves as a showcase of the region's potential and connects it to a global network of stakeholders eager to collaborate.

FIGURE. 2 EmpoWomen booth at PODIM

FIGURE. 3 EmpoWomen Startups at PODIM

During the event the EmpoWOMEN project proudly presented the first cohort of 11 women-led deep-tech startups from widening regions. As part of its mission to empower women entrepreneurs, the programme created a dynamic space for these startups to network, showcase their innovations, and engage in interactive sessions with key stakeholders from the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

FIGURE. 4 Startups Spaces at PODIM

A highlight of EmpoWOMEN’s involvement at PODIM was the panel discussion held on May 14, featuring Miguel García, Anna Tórz, Taryn Andersen, and Maja Horvat. Organized by the EmpoWOMEN project in collaboration with its sister project, Ready2Scale, as well as with the EIC funded project Women TechEU and the EU initiative Impulse4Women, this session aimed to increase awareness about the programme’s startups while emphasizing the importance of empowering women in technology and deep-tech industries.

FIGURE. 5 Panel at PODIM

During their participation in the PODIM conference, the EmpoWOMEN startups actively engaged in a wide range of activities to capitalise on the opportunities provided by the event. These included networking with potential investors, showcasing their products, initiating partnerships, and attending workshops and sessions to enhance their knowledge and visibility. Startups also leveraged media coverage and social media platforms to amplify their reach and attract further attention to their innovative solutions.

Table 5. PODIM Conference highlights in numbers

KPI	DESCRIPTION	RESULT
Leads Collected	Contact information from potential customers	11
Investor Meetings	Nº of meetings with potential investors	33
Partnerships Established	Nº of new partnerships initiated	16
Product Demos Conducted	Nº of product demonstrations performed	81
Workshops Attended	Nº of workshops or sessions attended	37
Social Media Engagement	Nº of engagements on social media posts	5,597
Media Publications	Nº of media or articles published	5

The outcomes of these efforts were detailed in the first-month reports, providing a comprehensive view of their achievements and impact.

3.6.2 SLUSH Conference

Slush is a not-for-profit organization on a mission to help and create founders to change the world. Based in Helsinki, Slush annually hosts the world’s leading startup event bringing together a curated crowd of European startups, world-class investors, and tech journalists. We stand by relevance over scale, bringing tangible value, and sharing actionable company-building advice. No fluff.

At the Slush event in Helsinki, the EmpoWOMEN startups continued to actively engage in various activities designed to maximize their exposure and networking opportunities. With a shared booth at the event, they showcased their innovations to a diverse audience and participated in one-on-one meetings with investors, corporates, and mentors. These interactions aimed to foster meaningful connections, explore potential collaborations, and further solidify their presence in the deep-tech ecosystem. While these efforts were undoubtedly impactful, detailed information about the outcomes achieved by the startups during Slush was not yet available at the time of the deliverable submission.

FIGURE. 6 EmpoWOMEN Startups at SLUSH

3.7 Investors voucher (vouchers)

As part of the programme, all startups were provided with an investor voucher, granting them access to Part 2 webinars organized by BAE, which focused on Investment Readiness topics. These sessions enabled participants to engage directly with investors and business angels.

The attendance rate for these webinars was nearly 100%, reflecting the startups’ strong interest and commitment to enhancing their fundraising knowledge. Feedback from participants was overwhelmingly positive.

Startups highly valued the quality of the content, as it addressed common challenges faced during their entrepreneurial journeys. Key topics included:

- Identifying the right investors and determining a suitable fit.
- Developing an effective funding strategy.
- Preparing necessary documentation for fundraising.
- Understanding the collaboration process with investors, including the due diligence phase.

This segment of the programme played a critical role in equipping startups with the tools and insights needed to navigate the complex landscape of investment and funding.

4. PROFILE OF PARTICIPANTS

4.1 Participant Startups – EmpoWOMEN Cohort 1

Table 6. Short Summary of Participant Startups

STARTUP NAME	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE
Astroteq.ai	Earthquake monitoring and forecasting based on space technologies.	www.astroteq.ai
GMZ Enerji	Developing non-flourinated nanofiber ion exchange membranes for fuel cell and electrolyzer systems, which are green hydrogen technologies	www.gmzenerji.com
GOTECH Antimicrobial	Solving medical device-related infection.	www.gotechantim.com

STARTUP NAME	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE
Heilo sp. z o.o.	Heilo offers a cover with built-in air-purifier for baby prams and strollers protecting babies from breathing toxic, polluted air.	www.heilo.eu
HUGUP	Revolutionising maternity care with our 3D-knitted support wear designed to enhance comfort and wellbeing for expectant mothers.	www.hugup.com
Innosensus, JSC	We are creating a personal gluten biosensor, which quickly detects the presence of gluten in the food, and helps to prevent unpleasant symptoms for gluten intolerant people & with celiace disease.	www.innosensus.com
IPLEXMED	IPLEXMED is developing NexaGuard, a first in class, portable, lab-grade and easy-to-use platform for the diagnosis of multiple infections and associated antimicrobial resistance in 20 min for Emergency Rooms.	www.iplexmed.com
IQ BIOZOOM	IQ Biozoom is developing technology for non-invasive home diagnostics. The company is working on innovative devices for measuring the concentration of biochemical substances in liquid analytes such as saliva, sweat, urine, tears. Currently, as part of the work on the technology, non-invasive home tests are being developed, measuring the level of glucose and lactates in saliva, and in the near future - also hormones and CRP proteins.	www.iqbiozoom.com
P-Agro Minerals	Recovering Phosphorus from Wastewater for fertilizer purposes.	www.p-agro-minerals
Pinky Tech	We make cybersecurity accessible with our Virtual CISO for SMEs, a real alternative to the serious shortage of skilled IT security professionals.	www.pinkycs.com

STARTUP NAME	DESCRIPTION	WEBSITE
The Newsroom	<p>Our AI analyses thousands of news articles daily. It identifies and summarises consensus and different perspectives.</p> <p>Through this, readers get a rounded view of what’s happening on our mobile app; journalists write high-quality articles faster, through our News AI co-pilot.</p>	<p>www.thenewsroom.ai</p>

4.2 Demographic Information

4.2.1 Founder’s demographics

- **Gender:** all 11 startups were female-founded startups, and at least 50% of the other team members were females.
- **Age:** the age group represented 25-45.
- **Nationality:** Polish, Moldovan, Lithuanian, Latvian, Portuguese, Turkish
- **Startup Location:** Widening Area Countries: Poland (4), Moldova (1), Lithuania (1), Latvia (1), Portugal (3), Turkey (1).

4.3 Industry Sectors and Technologies Represented

4.3.1 Sectors

Industries and areas where the startups are operating.

- SpaceTech
- Energy
- Materials & Chemicals
- Engineering
- Medical Devices
- Science
- HealthTech
- Robotics
- IoT (Internet of Things)
- Fashion
- Sustainable Materials
- Wellness & Beauty

- Software & Services
- Electronic Equipment
- FoodTech
- CleanTech & Waste Management
- AgriTech
- Circular Economy
- Cybersecurity
- Media
- Data Analytics, Management & Big Data

4.3.2 Technology

Core technologies and innovations that startups are using to develop their products and solutions.

- Deep Tech
- AI (Artificial Intelligence)
- Machine Learning
- Hardware
- Enterprise Software
- Biotechnology

4.4 Stage of Development of Participant Startups

All 11 startups in the Acceleration programme were in the early stages of product development, making this initiative an ideal fit for their needs. Feedback from the startups indicated high engagement levels throughout the programme, reflecting their commitment to growth and learning. The common KPIs that these startups focused on during the six months included:

4.4.1 Business Development

- Building a network and establishing industry positioning
- Outreach and meetings with potential customers
- Conducting market research and analysis
- Setting up a sales strategy and tools
- Initiating first sales and generating monthly revenue
- Establishing B2B2B partnerships
- Defining go-to-market strategy
- Developing a marketing strategy
- Collecting feedback from beta testers

- Compiling product documentation and user guides
- Creating a technological plan for the next three years
- Preparing documentation for the certification process
- Enhancing credibility and visibility in the market
- Boosting the company's credibility and scientific recognition regarding its technology
- Expanding the Research and Development (R&D) team
- Signing the first Letters of Intent (LOIs)
- Identifying necessary documents and certificates for export
- Applying for trademark registration
- Submitting patents and developing an intellectual property (IP) plan
- Implementing a prototype to meet regulatory requirements
- Conducting interviews with potential partners
- Defining the Ideal Customer Persona (ICP), including industry specifics
- Conducting customer interviews

4.4.2 Technology and Product Development

- Refining and validating prototypes
- Releasing new features
- Establishing testing environments and procedures
- Enhancing UI/UX design
- Releasing solutions for beta testing
- Expanding the network of tech experts in the industry for consultation
- Improving product performance indicators through better technology and solutions
- Developing a product roadmap for future stages
- Increasing the accuracy of test results
- Finalizing product design
- Creating product instructions
- Establishing contracts with partner companies for product development
- Developing packaging
- Selecting companies for prototype production
- Defining clinical study design and host institutions
- Standardizing production and analysis processes for product components

4.4.3 Investment Readiness

- Identifying the most suitable funding types and approaches, along with a fundraising strategy

- Compiling a list of relevant investors and funding sources
- Creating a compelling investor pitch deck
- Preparing for due diligence processes with potential investors
- Developing a financial forecasting plan

This structured approach not only facilitated the startups' growth but also laid a strong foundation for their future success in the competitive deep-tech landscape.

4.5 Founders Background and Experience

The founders' backgrounds and expertise are incredibly diverse, and after thorough analysis, it became evident that their skill sets perfectly aligned with their startups' product needs. This alignment not only demonstrated the founders' deep passion for their innovations but also justified one of the key elements of their journey: the "Why" behind their work.

In addition to their own expertise, all the founders have strong team members, each contributing a broad range of skills necessary for product development and business growth. Through participation in the Acceleration programme, the founders also identified areas where additional expertise was required. This discovery led many of them to initiate future hiring plans, ensuring their startups would have the talent needed to continue advancing their products

Table 7. Startup Founder

STARTUP NAME	FOUNDERS EXPERIENCE
<p>Astroteq.ai</p>	<p>The founder is a passionate researcher and entrepreneur known for her interdisciplinary approach, particularly in theoretical physics, dense matter, and astrophysics. As the co-founder of AstroTectonic, she explores the intersections of astronomy and geology, advancing research in areas like cosmoseismology. She also co-leads the Credo Cosmoseismic Group at <i>credo.science</i>, contributing to innovative research in this emerging field.</p> <p>In addition to her scientific achievements, she brings expertise in operations, business development, and management, making her a key player in technology-focused ventures. Her deep knowledge of mathematical models and numerical simulations enhances her ability to provide strategic insights and solutions, particularly for interdisciplinary projects that bridge science and technology.</p>

STARTUP NAME	FOUNDERS EXPERIENCE
<p>GMZ Enerji</p>	<p>Founder and System Design Leader with expertise in several cutting-edge areas, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fuel Cells: Focus on energy conversion and power generation systems. ● Nanotechnology: Specializing in the manipulation of materials on a molecular scale. ● Electrospin Method: Expertise in fabricating nanofibers using electrospinning for various applications. ● Experiment Design and Optimization: Proficient in structuring experiments to improve efficiency and outcomes. ● Energy Efficiency: Dedicated to developing systems and technologies that optimize energy use. <p>Her background places her at the forefront of innovation in energy and materials science.</p>
<p>GOTECH Antimicrobial</p>	<p>Seasoned biomedical engineer with over 10 years of experience. She is the co-founder, Chief Operating Officer (COO), and Chief Scientific Officer (CSO) of her current venture. Her academic journey is marked by a PhD in Medical Bioengineering, where she specialized in developing innovative strategies to combat bacterial infections in medical environments.</p> <p>During her MSc, she worked on polymeric microspheres aimed at removing <i>Helicobacter pylori</i> from the stomach, and her PhD research focused on developing antibacterial solutions using graphene and graphene-based materials to address infections related to dialysis catheters. With her deep expertise and leadership in both scientific research and business operations, she is driving impactful innovations in healthcare.</p>
<p>Heilo sp. z o.o.</p>	<p>Co-founder and CEO of her current venture, with extensive experience in operations, marketing management, and brand building. As an entrepreneur, she has a strong track record of driving marketing communication strategies and supporting startup growth.</p>
<p>HUGUP</p>	<p>A health tech entrepreneur and the founder/CEO of her current venture. With an entrepreneurial spirit and mindset, she has a proven track record of initiating impactful projects and infusing them with strategic business perspectives. Having navigated the digital industry through her roles at Digitas UK and UNIT9, and successfully running her own e-commerce agency, White Ducky, she is now channeling her expertise into the</p>

STARTUP NAME	FOUNDERS EXPERIENCE
	<p>medtech sector. As an entrepreneur experimenter, she is passionate about innovating and driving meaningful advancements in healthcare technology.</p>
<p>Innosensus, JSC</p>	<p>Co-founder and CEO of her current venture. With 13+ years of project management expertise, she has led numerous initiatives and projects to success. She is also a business management expert, specializing in digital marketing and strategy development for over a decade, with a keen focus on brand awareness.</p> <p>In addition, she has 5+ years of experience in export management and sales. Her academic role as a lecturer at Vilnius College (Lithuania) includes teaching Innovation and New Product Development, helping to shape the next generation of business innovators.</p> <p>As a board member of the export leaders programme "Wings" and a member of the Lithuanian Marketing Association, she continues to make a significant impact on Lithuania's export and marketing sectors.</p>
<p>IPLEXMED</p>	<p>PhD CBO and Co-founder of her current venture, bringing over 10 years of experience in team and project management as well as 9 years of expertise in public relations and communication. With a strong background in cellular and molecular biology, she has worked across a range of prestigious institutions in Europe and the USA, including IMS Aberdeen (UK), École Normale Supérieure (France), NYU (USA), IMM Lisbon, and ICVS Braga (Portugal).</p>
<p>IQ BIOZOOM</p>	<p>An experienced entrepreneur with a strong background in sales, communication, and marketing. She has accumulated several years of experience in building and developing new projects, particularly in these areas.</p> <p>Her career includes working with international corporations such as Deutsche Bank and CEZ, as well as collaborating with well-known global and local brands like UNICEF, CCC, DRE, and DOZ Pharmacies. A keen observer of how enterprises evolve through technological innovations, she is now focused on running and developing deep-tech startups as the CEO and co-founder.</p>
<p>P-Agro Minerals</p>	<p>CEO of a deep-tech startup and holds expertise in environmental engineering and sustainable energy, complemented by a Master of Business Administration. Her</p>

STARTUP NAME	FOUNDERS EXPERIENCE
	academic background spans various areas of business and management, providing her with a well-rounded skill set.
Pinky Tech	CEO and Product Owner of her venture with over 10 years of experience in the banking and FinTech sectors. Her extensive background encompasses product management, as well as cybersecurity and compliance management. She is certified in cybersecurity by (ISC2), underscoring her commitment to maintaining high standards of security and compliance in financial services. Her leadership and expertise position her as a key player in driving innovation and ensuring robust security measures within her organization.
The Newsroom	CEO of her venture, holding a master's degree in management. She has led B2B sales for Google’s largest customers and managed a multi-million-dollar client portfolio. With a strong background in solution engineering, she has successfully painted a vision for digital transformation tailored to scale-ups, helping them navigate their growth journey effectively.

5. DESCRIPTION OF SERVICES PROVIDED

5.1 Workshops and Educational Sessions

Throughout the Acceleration programme, a series of workshops and educational sessions were provided by Startup Wise Guys (SWG) and Business Angels Europe (BAE), designed to equip the participating female founders with essential knowledge and practical skills to accelerate the growth of their deep tech startups. These sessions covered a wide range of topics critical to startup development, from product validation and customer acquisition to investment readiness and scaling strategies.

The educational services were tailored to meet the specific needs of each startup, ensuring that they had access to relevant resources and expert insights to achieve their goals. Below is a detailed list of the workshops and educational sessions provided during the programme.

Table 8. Workshops and Educational Sessions

NAME	"Welcome session"
PURPOSE	The Welcome Session served as a key introductory event for all participants, including representatives from Sploro, Startup Wise Guys, Business Angels Europe, and Tech

	Ukraine. Led by Programme Lead, the session aimed to familiarize startups with the programme's key players and structure. It included partner introductions, a detailed explanation of the programme's main deliverables, an overview of the Acceleration Programme timeline, and a breakdown of the topics and tasks to be covered in Part 1 and Part 2.
CONCLUSIONS	Startups left the session with a clear understanding of the programme's objectives, deliverables, and next steps for successful enrollment and active participation.

NAME	Webinar " Programme Goals & KPIs "
PURPOSE	<p>The primary objective of this session was to review the goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the Acceleration programme, ensuring a clear understanding of the criteria for successful completion. Startups also had the opportunity to raise any remaining questions or concerns regarding the requirements for programme success and grant qualification.</p> <p>Led by Programme Lead, the session included representatives from Sploro and Business Angels Europe. The discussions provided valuable insights into the programme's expectations and deliverables.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	Following the session, startups gained a clearer understanding of the functionality of mentorship and tech event vouchers, mandatory tasks, the importance of attending live sessions, and the key steps required to qualify for the grant.

NAME	Peer to Peer " Myths and Stereotypes of female-led deep tech startups "
PURPOSE	The primary aim of this session was to foster deeper connections and engagement among participants, offering an open forum for like-minded individuals to discuss the common myths and stereotypes faced by female founders in the deep tech startup ecosystem. Startup founders shared personal experiences and provided practical advice on how to navigate these challenges.
CONCLUSIONS	After the session, many founders expressed appreciation for the opportunity to engage in such an insightful conversation. A recurring theme in the discussion was the heightened pressure on women to prove their skills and knowledge compared to their male counterparts. However, once they demonstrated their competence, they earned the respect and trust of others. Despite these successes, the conversation highlighted

	that unequal treatment compared to men remains a significant issue within the industry.
NAME	Q&A “ Goal-setting ”
PURPOSE	The session began with a presentation on the concept of SMART goals, highlighting common mistakes made during the goal-setting process. Following this, the coach reviewed each startup's individual goals and KPIs, offering advice on necessary adjustments. Several startups required guidance on how to differentiate between tasks and goals. Additionally, the session addressed the importance of setting proper priorities and managing dependencies, with the coach explaining how poor planning in these areas could hinder product development.
CONCLUSIONS	It became evident that many startups struggled to distinguish between tasks and actual goals. Following the session, the startups acknowledged the need to revisit and revise their existing Goal Setting & KPIs templates, implementing the coach’s suggestions and newly acquired insights.
NAME	Peer to Peer “ Purpose and Values ”
PURPOSE	All the startups engaged in insightful discussions centered around their company purpose and values. The feedback from participants indicated that the session was both inspirational and empowering, as it allowed them to share their personal stories and "Whys," while also hearing from other founders.
CONCLUSIONS	Peer-to-peer sessions were highly regarded as valuable opportunities for founders and their teams to exchange experiences, share their stories, and gain inspiration from others. These sessions fostered a sense of community and deeper understanding among participants.
NAME	Q&A “ Problem Definition ”
PURPOSE	The session began with a presentation on crafting a solid problem statement. Following the presentation, the coach reviewed the problem statements of startups that were willing to share, including P-Agro Minerals, The Newsroom, Innosensus, HUGUP, GOTECH, Heilo, and IPLEXMED, offering tailored advice on how to improve and refine their statements

CONCLUSIONS	The startups found this session highly valuable, even those who didn't present their problem statements. Listening to the feedback and discussions helped them gain a better understanding of how to refine their own problem and solution statements.
NAME	Peer to Peer "Pitching"
PURPOSE	Startups had the opportunity to pitch their ideas and receive feedback from their peers. The session was regarded as valuable, with many insights and constructive suggestions being shared.
CONCLUSIONS	The session fostered a sense of community among the startups, as they showed genuine interest in supporting and helping each other. However, most startups exceeded the 3-minute pitch limit, highlighting the need for them to refine and update their pitch decks to stay within the time constraints.
NAME	Webinar "Women and complex tech solutions"
PURPOSE	The coach shared her experiences as a founder in the deep tech sector, discussing the challenges she encountered along the way. She emphasized the importance of engaging with female-led startup communities to share experiences and support one another. Furthermore, she highlighted that it's crucial to start thinking about scaling up already in the MVP stage and gave practical advice on how to quickly attract early adopters without unnecessary delays.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups appreciated hearing a real success story from a female-led deep tech startup. They were also pleased with the insightful answers they received to their questions.
NAME	Q&A "MVP and Planning"
PURPOSE	The session began with a presentation on the crucial elements of an MVP and how to effectively plan product development. The coach explained how to differentiate between truly essential features and those that are just "nice to have." Following the presentation, startups had the opportunity to ask questions, with some sharing their product development plans. The coach offered valuable advice on digging deeper into every aspect of product development and recommended several project management tools.

CONCLUSIONS	The startups were highly satisfied with the session, gaining valuable insights and practical knowledge to apply to their product development processes.
NAME	Peer to Peer “Tough Questions”
PURPOSE	The session began with explaining the importance of asking tough questions related to investor readiness and having clear answers prepared. Although startups were already familiar with the examples of tough questions, it was clear that some still struggled to define precise responses. After returning from the breakout rooms, many startups shared that these sessions were very therapeutic and necessary. Discussing various topics not only helped them structure their thinking more effectively but also supported their decision-making processes.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups were highly satisfied with the session, noting that Peer to Peer sessions are invaluable. These sessions provide a safe and inspiring environment for discussing not only product development but also various business aspects, helping to shape their overall strategies.
NAME	Webinar “Pitching”
PURPOSE	The session kicked off with a presentation on best pitching practices, where the coach outlined different types of pitches and how to tailor them for various audiences. Startups engaged by asking specific questions about their pitch decks, focusing on areas where they were struggling.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups gained invaluable insights into how to craft memorable pitch decks and learned key dos and don’ts when pitching. After the session, the coach also shared additional resources on Slack to further support the startups in refining their pitches.
NAME	Webinar “Deep tech project and time management”
PURPOSE	Startups had the opportunity to hear from a speaker, herself a deep tech startup founder, who shared her experience in managing such projects. Her key message was not to fear releasing early and seeking feedback, even if the product is far from perfect. She emphasized the importance of hiring the right people—those who believe in the idea and are passionate about its future development, not just motivated by money.

	The speaker also suggested scheduling time for rest and personal activities to maintain balance. As a female founder, she acknowledged encountering skepticism, but she chose to focus on acting as a founder rather than dwelling on this issue
CONCLUSIONS	The startups were very pleased and felt encouraged by hearing firsthand experiences. It helped them realize that everyone faces similar challenges, reinforcing the idea that they are on the right path.

NAME	Peer to Peer "Life Hacks"
PURPOSE	In the breakout rooms, startups discussed their life habits and daily routines. A key takeaway from the session was the importance of not feeling guilty when sometimes needing to say no to personal time or family gatherings, and conversely, saying no to startup-related responsibilities to spend time with loved ones. As a result of these discussions, a new Slack channel, "Books to Read," was created where startups began sharing recommendations for books covering various life aspects.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups gained valuable insights into how others manage their lives and balance responsibilities. Understanding that they share similar challenges helped them feel more united and supported by their peers.

NAME	Q&A "How to set up SDG goals"
PURPOSE	This session was modified from the original plan, which was to check on the startups' progress toward their set goals. At the request of the startups, the focus shifted to discussing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Given the coach's solid expertise in this area, a 2-hour session was held where the coach explained the SDG process and key considerations. At the end of the session, startups shared their SDG goals, which were reviewed, and they received personalized advice from the coach.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups expressed gratitude for the session, as their prior knowledge of SDGs was limited. Following the session, they are now working on developing their SDG goals, which will add significant value to their projects.

NAME	Q&A "Sales"
PURPOSE	During the session, startups raised questions about how to hire a salesperson, what factors to consider, and how to manage the B2B sales process. The most prominent topic

	discussed was how to initiate the sales process while the product is still in the prototype or development stage.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups felt encouraged to start planning their sales strategies and begin reaching out to potential customers, even at the early stages of product development. They also gained valuable insights into how to find the right sales representative for their companies.
NAME	Peer to Peer "Brand"
PURPOSE	Startups presented their brand visuals and shared the stories behind their chosen company names. After receiving peer feedback, nearly 70% of the startups indicated they would consider making changes, either to their existing visuals or even the company name itself. It was also discussed that some startups need to think about how to position their company name in alignment with future plans, especially if they plan to create separate products that may require different names.
CONCLUSIONS	This was a highly valuable session, as startups gained a deeper understanding of how their chosen names and visuals resonate with others. There is still work to be done to solidify their brands, ensuring they stand out and that their company names clearly communicate what the business does at a glance.
NAME	Training "Pitch Drills"
PURPOSE	All the startups participated in this training, where the coach provided advice on various aspects of their pitch presentations. Startups gained valuable insights tailored to their specific needs.
CONCLUSIONS	This session was highly valuable, as it addressed numerous questions, doubts, and concerns. The startups particularly appreciated the 1-on-1 nature of the session, which allowed them to focus on their individual cases and receive personalized guidance.
NAME	Q&A "Fundraising"
PURPOSE	The coach addressed all the startups' questions related to fundraising. A significant takeaway was that many startups felt unsure about how to reach out to investors and how to determine which investors would be appropriate for them. The coach encouraged startups to conduct cross-references and connect with other startups that have

	previously worked with potential investors. The discussion on red flags in fundraising was particularly engaging for the startups.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups now have greater clarity on how to identify potential investors, approach them effectively, and make informed decisions regarding their fundraising efforts.

NAME	Fireside chat " Women journey in deep tech "
PURPOSE	<p>We invited two guest speakers, CEOs of deep tech startups, who addressed all the startups' questions and encouraged them to remain true to themselves and their products. They emphasized that there isn't a one-size-fits-all plan and that decisions made by investors, partners, and customers are often emotional. The speakers urged startups to disregard the stereotype of seeing predominantly older white men in the room, encouraging them to be themselves and maintain self-confidence. They stressed the importance of believing in their work, even when faced with skepticism about its potential.</p> <p>Additionally, they highlighted the value of a strong network, advising startups to actively participate in conferences and events to expand their contacts and gain introductions.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	The startups received this session positively, appreciating the firsthand experiences shared by the speakers. They felt encouraged and understood, reinforcing their confidence in their journeys.

NAME	Peer to Peer " Communication "
PURPOSE	During the session in breakout rooms, startups discussed the topic of communication, sharing the channels they currently use and identifying areas where they still face challenges. By the end of the session, they acknowledged that their understanding of this topic had significantly improved—from a rating of 3 out of 10 at the beginning of the programme to at least 7 out of 10, leaving room for further improvement.
CONCLUSIONS	This was a valuable session, allowing startups to share their challenges and gain insights from their peers.

NAME	Q&A " Legal "
PURPOSE	The coach addressed all the questions posed by the startups, most of which focused on intellectual property (IP) issues. Key discussions included how to choose the right lawyer

	and best practices for legal representation—whether to work with one lawyer or multiple specialists for different legal matters.
CONCLUSIONS	Finding the appropriate lawyer can be challenging, and startups were encouraged to consult with their peers to identify the best match for their specific needs.
NAME	Online event PROGRESS DAY
PURPOSE	<p>All the startups participated in the session, which began with opening remarks. Each startup had 3 minutes to pitch their ideas, followed by 5 minutes for questions from the audience, including representatives from Business Angels Europe (BAE) and lead coaches. The startups received insightful questions that sparked meaningful discussions.</p> <p>At the end of the session, a BAE representative outlined the summer break assignment and what startups can expect in Part 2 of the programme. It was evident that all the startups had achieved significant progress over the 8 weeks of Part 1.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	The session showcased the advancements made by the startups and set the stage for continued growth in the next phase of the programme.
NAME	Peer to Peer “Welcome back”
PURPOSE	All participants discussed their experiences during the summer break. The startups collectively agreed on the importance of taking a vacation to rest and recharge, allowing them to return fully dedicated to developing their products. They expressed satisfaction with the summer break assignment, which focused on creating a financial plan and identifying investment needs. This task helped them avoid procrastination and address an essential aspect of their business.
CONCLUSIONS	The startups collectively expressed that they are full of energy to continue with the programme activities and are already working hard to achieve their KPIs set for Part 2.
NAME	Webinar “Introduction in Investment Readiness programme ”
PURPOSE	The session was an introduction to the overall investment readiness programme and what will be covered in the weeks ahead

	The session included an opportunity for participants to ask questions about the Investment readiness programme and to each say a little about their Fundraising experience so far challenges and successes (reflection on what they have learned so far).
CONCLUSIONS	The startups had been able to consider their own business and finance needs and of their experiences and lessons learned so far.
NAME	Webinar " Fundraising strategy and Investment Proposal "
PURPOSE	Provided an in depth understanding of how investors will evaluate an investment opportunity from a deep tech business and in depth insight of some of the challenges and barriers that they may experience as a woman deep tech business. This session also covered how to develop a clear investment opportunity that indicates their strengths and potential and which may overcome any potential gender bias.
CONCLUSIONS	Participants gained better understanding of how an investor thinks and how they will approach key elements of their investment proposal what they will need to consider and think about when presenting to investors.
NAME	Webinar " Investor Toolkit "
PURPOSE	Designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to develop an effective and comprehensive Toolkit to meet the requirements of investors and prepare for direct engagement with investors.
CONCLUSIONS	Participants gained a strong understanding of all the key elements and components that are needed to start their engagement with investors and what is needed to address investors information needs. They gained practical tips and what this means for women in deeptech.
NAME	Peer to Peer " Building credibility in male-dominated industry "
PURPOSE	In a peer-to-peer session on building credibility in a male-dominated industry, 80% of the participants expressed that they struggle significantly with being recognized as equal players. The remaining 20% shared practical advice on handling situations where their credibility is questioned or where they experience disregard in male-dominated settings. They encouraged their peers to maintain confidence even in challenging situations.

CONCLUSIONS	It was concluded that the business world should be one where gender does not matter. Participants emphasized the importance of working on self-confidence and making a strong first impression. Practices such as a firm handshake and maintaining eye contact were highlighted as effective strategies for those who may be hesitant to adopt them.
NAME	Webinar " Making a winning Pitch to Investors "
PURPOSE	Provided a detailed overview of the key topics, including graphical information, relevant insights from the individual investor, practical examples and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur. The session also provided advice and tips on presentation skills and how to engage with investors.
CONCLUSIONS	The participants gained insights and understanding of what investors expected from pitch and how to increase their chances to attract investor attention and successfully engage with the investors.
NAME	MENTOR DAY
PURPOSE	A dedicated Mentor Day was organized, allowing each startup to choose up to 6 mentoring sessions, each lasting 45 minutes. The mentor pool covered a wide range of expertise, including finances, fundraising, sales, leadership, branding, business development, go-to-market strategy, and community management. On average, startups signed up for 4 to 6 sessions.
CONCLUSIONS	The information, support, and knowledge received during the sessions were invaluable, and the startups were grateful and overly satisfied. They made numerous new connections and continued to communicate with the mentors even beyond the project activities.
NAME	Webinar " Due Dilligence "
PURPOSE	The session provided understanding of how to effectively follow up with investors following the pitching session and to ensure investor interest. The second half of this session was designed to give an in depth understanding of how to prepare for and engage in the due diligence process. This included understanding the core elements of the business and investment proposition that were looked at in depth

	ensuring that they have gathered all of the relevant data evidence and information to address the investor’s concerns and issues in a timely and effective and confident way.
CONCLUSIONS	The women entrepreneurs gained increased understanding of how investors conduct due diligence particularly at Angel and early stage investment level and their approach to the five core areas enabled them to gain more in depth insight into how the investors themselves approach this key area in the investment process.
NAME	Peer to Peer “Financial Literacy and Funding strategies”
PURPOSE	The purpose of this session was to share knowledge about finances and funding among participants. By this point, they were halfway through Investment Readiness Part 2, which facilitated fruitful conversations and allowed them to share real use cases along with suggestions on fundraising topics and valuable resources.
CONCLUSIONS	Participants demonstrated a significantly higher level of understanding and confidence in discussing these topics compared to the beginning of the programme.
NAME	Webinar “Negotiation and the Term Sheet”
PURPOSE	This session was designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to engage with and negotiate with investors in order to achieve a Termsheet as an indication of the commitment to make an investment and how to successfully manage the negotiation process. The aim of the session was to give an in depth understanding of the key terms of the termsheet and how this relates to the due diligence process, building on the previous session; how to respond to the details information and evidence requirements to ensure that investors are satisfied; providing a clear understanding of some of the pitfalls and challenges in achieving a successful and satisfactory termsheet.
CONCLUSIONS	The participants felt better equipped to more confidently negotiate and gain the outcome of the type of investment and level of investment they require, whilst at the same time understanding that the process may breakdown and their opportunities to walk away from the process if this does not feel right.
NAME	Webinar How to value your deep tech business
PURPOSE	This session was designed to give an in-depth understanding of how to value your business for investment purposes and how to understand the approach that investors

	<p>are likely to make in understanding the valuation of your business and the methodologies that can be applied and that this frequently more of an art than a science and the importance of creating a flexible approach to negotiation. A final aspect of this session was to gain an overall understanding of how to approach the structure of the deal in relation to the valuation and finance needs and the benefits of both direct equity deals , or those based on convertible loan notes and advanced security mechanisms that establish the valuation over a period of time the benefits and the negatives of the different approaches in the context a valuation and successfully accessing investment.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	<p>The participants gained practical understanding and parameters for valuation of a deep tech business, whilst having a clearer understanding of the approach and requirements of investors and better understanding the points of negotiation and potential conflict.</p>
NAME	Peer to Peer "Negotiation and deal-making"
PURPOSE	<p>The purpose of this session was to explore techniques for successful negotiation and deal-making specifically tailored to deep tech startups. Participants shared real-life experiences and discussed their biggest challenges in the field.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	<p>The participants concluded that a significant challenge in negotiations is a lack of confidence, often tied to the early-stage status of their products. Nonetheless, they recognize that developing negotiation skills is crucial for their success and are actively seeking resources to improve. Thorough preparation for negotiation meetings was emphasized as essential to help them feel in control and boost their confidence throughout the process.</p>
NAME	Webinar "Legal Process"
PURPOSE	<p>This session provided an in-depth understanding of the legal and contractual aspects of closing the deal, providing a detailed understanding of the core documents; what the various terms and requirements mean; and that the contractual requirements and protections are clearly understood.</p>
CONCLUSIONS	<p>The participants increased their understanding of the legal process and the purpose and benefits of the core legal documents. They understood better what is their relationship to the investors post investment, the protections on both sides and felt more confident in their knowledge of the relevant documentation and technical aspects.</p>

NAME	Webinar “ Post Investment ”
PURPOSE	This session focused on the relationship with investors after the deal is done to provide an in depth understanding of how to effectively work with investors to get the most out of their experience, expertise, introductions, knowledge and support which provides important added value to the business post investment.
CONCLUSIONS	The entrepreneurs understood better how to make the investor relationship work effectively -the do's and don'ts of how to work together. They also understood how to start planning of the next round of investment as the business grows and how to position their business for next stage funding.
NAME	Peer to Peer “ Cultivating Leadership skills ”
PURPOSE	The purpose of this session was to explore techniques for developing leadership skills and strategies essential for effectively leading a deep tech startup. Participants engaged in discussions about the challenges and opportunities of leadership in the dynamic and demanding context of startup management.
CONCLUSIONS	Several participants acknowledged gaps in their leadership skills and expressed a strong commitment to improving in this area. There was a shared understanding among the participants that as startup founders, it is crucial to develop not only strong leadership abilities but also effective management skills. Emphasis was placed on the importance of mastering time management and prioritization to navigate the complexities of running a startup successfully. This session highlighted the participants' dedication to personal and professional growth, recognizing that these skills are integral to their journey as startup leaders.

5.2 Mentoring and Coaching

One of the most valuable aspects of the Acceleration programme was the face-to-face meetings with mentors and coaches. The project team carefully selected the most appropriate experts for live workshops, with 99% of them being female coaches. Feedback was gathered after each session from all parties, and it was overwhelmingly positive. These insights played a critical role in the programme’s success, demonstrating that investing time in finding the best mentors and coaches is vital for initiatives like this.

These interactions not only helped participants expand their networks significantly but also offered a deeper understanding of how businesses operate across different countries and regions, encouraging a global

perspective. Many new connections were established, and several mentors continued providing invaluable advice and feedback even after the sessions ended. By unlocking their networks, they helped these aspiring female entrepreneurs accelerate progress toward achieving their business, product, and investment goals.

5.3 Access to Funding and Investment Opportunities

A key element of the Investment readiness programme provided by BAE was the direct interaction with investors throughout the webinar programme delivery. Each webinar was presented by either two investors or one investor, providing direct insights from investors on how investors approach deeptech businesses, their requirements and how to effectively meet their investment needs and how to engage and negotiate effectively. Notably the programme offered direct access to experienced women investors, with all but one of the investors delivering the webinars being women Angels or Women VCs who provided deep understanding and direct insight into the challenges for women entrepreneurs in attracting investment and gave strong advice and support to areas such as investor engagement, negotiation and addressing investor bias. Throughout the investment readiness programme, there were direct opportunities for follow between the women entrepreneurs and women investors who were all members of leading Angel network and syndicates across Europe and provided a direct channel to these networks.

In addition, BAE has offered all of the programme participants the opportunity to attend a dedicated Investor presentation and feedback session on 19th December 2024 as an integral part of the experience for the Cohort 1 deep tech businesses. This event attended by a group of selected investors from across BAE's investment community across Europe will enable each team to have a dedicated slot to present their investment proposition to the investors and gain direct feedback from the investors on the level of investment readiness and investor attractiveness and what more they will need to do to increase their potential to attract investment. The event will include opportunities for follow up connections and meetings with the investor's own networks and syndicates with the potential to access investment or gain interest from investors as potential investment opportunities, leading to potential deals in 2025.

5.4 Networking Opportunities and Community Building

Throughout the EmpoWOMEN Acceleration Programme, several community-building opportunities were provided for both the participants and the project's partners:

PODIM Conference, Maribor: At the beginning of the Acceleration Programme, all startups and project partners were invited to attend the PODIM conference in Maribor. This event provided startups with the chance to showcase their products and connect with potential partners and investors. For the project

partners, it was an excellent opportunity to engage with the startups and promote the EmpoWOMEN initiative.

Fostering Collaboration and Confidence: During the Acceleration Programme, participants valued not only the educational aspects but also the opportunity to meet other female founders and role models. These interactions facilitated discussions on a variety of topics, offering encouragement and boosting the participants' self-confidence. Daily exchanges of experiences, insights, and support among the participants helped to cultivate a strong female founder community.

Continued Mentorship and Collaboration: In addition to the formal mentoring sessions, many founders continued collaborating with their mentors beyond the programme, unlocking further networking and partnership opportunities.

Onsite Demo Day, Helsinki: At the conclusion of the Acceleration Programme, an onsite Demo Day was held in Helsinki, where all 11 startups participated, showcasing their progress to an audience of potential investors and stakeholders.

SLUSH Conference, Helsinki: Following the Demo Day, the startups attended the SLUSH conference, a major global tech event. Several startups were selected to participate in the Pitching Competition, which served as a strong indicator of the project's success in fostering their growth and enhancing their visibility.

Podcast Episodes: Podcast episodes were created for each of the founders, promoting the EmpoWOMEN project and allowing listeners to gain a deeper understanding of the impact this initiative has on the female entrepreneur ecosystem.

6. EXECUTION DETAILS

6.1 Programme Implementation Process

The implementation of the programme was smooth and well-organized. Each week, the content for Part 1 was unlocked, focusing on a specific topic. Startups received weekly updates outlining what to expect in the upcoming week, including any mandatory assignments. Feedback from participants highlighted the effectiveness of communication, with startups expressing appreciation for the prompt responses to their outstanding questions. Frequent and transparent communication emerged as a key factor in the programme's success. All deliverables from the startups were submitted on time, and every planned project activity was successfully executed according to schedule.

6.2 Challenges Faced During Execution

Despite the smooth execution, several challenges were encountered. One significant challenge for the participants was providing sufficient evidence for the achieved Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). However, this was successfully managed. At the programme's outset, there were concerns about a potential dropout rate, but ultimately, all 11 startups completed the programme successfully. Another challenge involved finding technology-specific mentors for ad-hoc meetings, which was also addressed effectively, with all requests fulfilled.

6.3 Adjustments and Improvements Made

Although the programme was already structured, adjustments were made to better meet the needs of the startups. For instance, instead of solely reviewing pre-set goals and KPIs, a session focused on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was introduced based on startup requests. While the original plan was to feature only female coaches, one session was led by a male coach to diversify the mentoring experience.

In preparation for Part 2, the initial plan was revised to provide startups with a report template in advance, enabling them to begin drafting their final deliverables. This proactive approach was highly valued by the participants. Additionally, startups learned the importance of gathering evidence for their achievements. As a result, a spreadsheet was created for each startup to record their KPI results as they were achieved, allowing lead coaches ample time to review and approve these accomplishments.

7. IMPACT ANALYSIS

7.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs for the Acceleration Programme set a structured framework for participant engagement and progress over six months. Here's a breakdown of each KPI:

1. **Defined Goals & KPIs Document:** Startups were required to establish clear goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the upcoming six months, divided into Part 1 and Part 2, ensuring that they aim to achieve them as per the established timeline.
2. **Attendance Rate:** Startups should have maintained at least a 75% attendance rate for all organized online programme activities, indicating a strong commitment to the programme's educational and collaborative elements.

3. **Lead Coach Sessions:** Each startup should have participated in at least 10 sessions with lead coaches, allowing them to receive ongoing guidance and personalized mentorship throughout the programme.
4. **Subject Matter Expert Sessions:** Based on each startup's unique needs, participants were expected to engage in at least six sessions with subject matter experts, covering key areas relevant to their growth and development.
5. **Tech Events Participation:** To gain exposure and network within the industry, startups were required to attend at least two organized tech events, giving them direct insights into current market trends and potential partnership opportunities.
6. **Pitch Presentation:** Startups were asked to prepare a concise, impactful three-minute pitch presentation, sharpening their messaging and pitching skills, which are critical in attracting investor interest.
7. **Financial Plan:** Startups were asked to develop a comprehensive financial plan, including projections and an outline of investment needs. This KPI ensures they're financially prepared and have clarity on their funding requirements.

These KPIs collectively worked to support startups in goal-setting, accountability, industry exposure, mentorship engagement, and readiness for funding opportunities.

7.2 Data Collection and Analysis Process

The Data Collection and Analysis Process utilized two primary methods to capture a full picture of startup progress and programme effectiveness:

1. **Comprehensive Data Collection:** This first method focused on gathering transparent, detailed data on key metrics of startup growth and the programme's overall impact. Startups were required to submit progress reports on their KPIs, and there was gathered feedback from mentors and experts who engaged with each startup individually. This dual approach offered a nuanced view, as feedback from direct mentoring sessions provided insight into each startup's specific challenges and accomplishments on an ongoing basis.
2. **Continuous Data Analysis for Programme Adaptation:** Weekly analysis of the collected data allowed for a real-time assessment of each startup's development path, enabling programme adjustments to address any challenges or to capitalize on emerging opportunities. This agile method ensured that startups received dynamic support, tailored to meet evolving needs and objectives.

Together, these methods facilitated a responsive, data-driven process, providing the foundation for effective, customized support that maximized outcomes for each participating startup.

8. RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

8.1 List of Participating Startups and Key Achievements

Table 9. Startup Key Achievements

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
<p>Astroreq.ai</p>	<p>The startup has achieved significant milestones during the programme, including advancements in product development, partnership building, and investment readiness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Signed 2 Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with Nepal NGOs and finalized 2 reseller agreements with insurance brokers, strengthening market outreach and collaboration. ● Organized a new pilot in Turkey to validate and refine the earthquake forecast system. ● Achieved Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6, with the earthquake forecast system now utilizing near-real-time data and historical data. The upcoming pilot aims to transition the system to real-time data. Additionally, the hardware is ready for small-batch manufacturing. ● Successfully integrated SAR satellite data into the system to enhance its capabilities and created three detectors for further development and testing. <p>These achievements not only demonstrate technical and strategic progress but also underscore the startup's readiness to scale and attract investment as it continues its journey.</p>
<p>GMZ Enerji</p>	<p>This startup has made significant strides in preparing their innovative product for market entry. Key accomplishments include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development of the first market-ready products with repeatable production and standardized analysis procedures. ● Establishment of preliminary agreements with potential customers for product testing. ● Standardization of membrane production in various sizes, ensuring consistent quality.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initiation of certification processes and application for intellectual property rights. ● The startup has also embraced circular economy principles by developing recycling processes for their products. <p>Thanks to the EmpoWOMEN programme, the team expanded its focus beyond product development to address critical market-entry requirements, such as certification, customs procedures, and sustainability measures. These efforts have positioned them to confidently enter the market.</p>
<p>GOTECH Antimicrobial</p>	<p>This startup has achieved critical milestones in both technological development and business strategy, solidifying its position as a promising innovator in the healthcare sector.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Advanced the production of the first prototype of GOcap, using a scalable technique in collaboration with a certified medical device company. ● Overcame significant challenges in identifying and aligning with the right certified manufacturer, marking a key step toward pilot-scale production. ● Progressed to Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL6) and is advancing toward TRL7, with the final steps of prototype optimization underway. ● Initiated partnerships with certified companies to align manufacturing protocols, ensuring smooth scaling from prototype to pilot production. ● Made significant strides in clinical trial preparation, including securing a partnership with a CRO and host institution, bringing them closer to validating the safety and performance of GOcap. ● Applied to the EIC Accelerator with a blended funding option, seeking significant funding to drive further development. ● Secured 9 Letters of Intent (LOIs) from 1 potential client, 2 manufacturers across 2 countries, and 6 Key Opinion Leaders (KOLs) from 4 countries, confirming unmet needs and validating the product-market fit. ● Established a strategic partnership with a major dialysis clinics group, demonstrating early market traction and potential for integration. ● Developed a comprehensive fundraising plan and exit strategy while building trust and connections with potential clients, manufacturers, and KOLs.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<p>These achievements highlight significant progress in preparing GOcap for market entry, with a clear pathway to starting sales in the EU by 2027. The startup’s parallel efforts in scaling production and preparing for clinical trials underline its commitment to meeting ambitious timelines and regulatory standards.</p>
<p>Heilo sp. z o.o.</p>	<p>This startup has made remarkable progress, achieving significant milestones in product development, market entry, and business growth:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Finalized the Minimum Viable Product (MVP), including a full list of accessories and suppliers. ● Certified the product to meet all EU regulatory requirements. ● Completed all documentation for the product and prepared it for serial production. ● Estimated production costs and successfully produced a small series of the product for testing with users. ● Reached the market-fit stage, enabling the commencement of targeted sales activities. ● Hired a dedicated sales manager to drive market expansion. ● Established initial collaborations with resellers in Poland, Germany, the Netherlands, and the Czech Republic, making the product available in six baby accessory stores. ● Expanded sales activities in Poland, Germany, and the Netherlands, with agreements in progress with distributors. ● Secured promotion by two Polish influencers, increasing brand visibility among target audiences. ● Received positive feedback from resellers and end users, with 60 out of 80 testers expressing an intention to purchase the product. ● Tested the product in seven cities across Poland and Germany, gathering critical user insights. ● Achieved exposure through television, press coverage, and social media campaigns. ● Collaborated with prominent influencers and foundations to further promote the product online.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Recognized as a finalist in the Polish Future Institute competition, enhancing credibility and visibility. ● Researched and identified optimal sales opportunities to refine sales and marketing processes. ● Developed strategies to create sustainable, long-term revenue streams. <p>These achievements showcase the startup’s ability to deliver a market-ready, certified product while establishing a strong foothold in key markets, laying the groundwork for sustained growth and future success.</p>
<p>HUGUP</p>	<p>This startup has made significant progress toward market entry, demonstrating strong alignment between product development, business strategy, and investor engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Attracted several promising leads and initiated discussions with potential investors, strengthening future funding opportunities. ● Finalized the business model and developed a comprehensive market launch strategy, ensuring a clear path to market. ● Streamlined the investment strategy to align with long-term growth objectives. ● Partnered with the Mother & Child Institute for wear tests, refining the prototype and enhancing product-market fit. ● Finalized the product prototype using advanced 3D knitting technology, ensuring quality and scalability. ● Developed a plan for sensor integration and identified a potential tech lead to oversee this critical feature in future iterations. <p>The product is fully finalized, and the production phase is planned, with a brand launch scheduled for the first half of 2025. These achievements highlight the startup’s readiness to introduce a well-crafted and market-ready solution to consumers, backed by strategic planning and innovation.</p>
<p>Innosensus, JSC</p>	<p>This startup has made notable progress in securing resources, refining its product, and establishing strategic partnerships to advance its gluten detection technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Secured a new grant opportunity worth €35,000 through a signed agreement. ● Prepared a comprehensive funding strategy to align future financial efforts with growth objectives.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Refined the B2B market focus through interviews with gluten-free food manufacturers, restaurant chains, pharmaceutical distributors, and corporate stakeholders (IT, insurance, and tech companies) interested in workplace prevention solutions. ● Compiled a list of potential B2B distributors and partners to drive market expansion. ● Signed two Letters of Intent (LOIs) with potential partners, validating market interest. ● Held impactful discussions with Sony and Samsung R&D departments, exploring potential collaborations in food technology detection systems. ● Developed a new prototype and finalized the product design. ● Refined the limited detection (LOD) capabilities of the gluten sensor, providing precise performance metrics. ● Transitioned the technology from laboratory conditions to real-world applications, a critical step toward commercialization. ● Created an IP strategy document to protect the startup’s innovative solutions and ensure market competitiveness. <p>These achievements highlight the startup’s progress in product development, market positioning, and strategic collaboration, setting the stage for future growth and impact in the gluten detection market.</p>
<p>IPLEXMED</p>	<p>This medtech startup has made significant progress in securing funding, advancing product development, and building a strong foundation for market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Secured €102,500 in non-dilutive funding, providing critical resources to support ongoing development and operations. ● Achieved clinical evidence, advancing to Technology Readiness Level 6 (TRL6), a pivotal milestone in product validation. ● Improved sensor performance, enhancing the functionality and reliability of the hardware and software solutions. ● Progressed with product development and clinical validation, ensuring the solution meets regulatory and market standards. ● Established key partnerships to support development and market entry efforts.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expanded the team, adding expertise and capacity to drive innovation and execution. <p>Although market entry will require additional time due to the complexities of medtech development, the startup is well-positioned for continued progress with a clear focus on achieving future milestones.</p>
IQ BIOZOOM	<p>This startup has made progress across multiple dimensions, including investment engagement, technological development, and market readiness.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Onboarded a Business Angel to support future growth. Established a partnership with Epcl, Switzerland. Conducted multiple investment presentations to attract potential funding. Improved the prototype and test strips, featuring a new and enhanced electronic circuit. Advanced to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 5, demonstrating market readiness and significant development progress. Introduced the technology to six potential clients, building awareness and creating opportunities for future collaborations. Achieved significant progress in pitching skills, effectively presenting to investors and stakeholders. Enhanced capabilities in operating within an international environment. Expanded networking efforts, building relationships critical to future scaling and market entry. <p>These achievements highlight the startup's dedication to technological progress, market readiness, and strategic growth, positioning it strongly for future milestones.</p>
P-Agro Minerals	<p>This startup has made remarkable progress in advancing its Letonite water filter technology and fertilizer product, demonstrating significant traction and strategic collaboration. Key achievements include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initiated two POC tests with industry companies in Germany and Northern Ireland to validate the Letonite filter solution. Established a partnership with a key technology partner in the Baltic market, paving the way for access to pilot customers in 2025.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Partnered with the Austrian Institute of Technology to co-develop a fertilizer product, leveraging their expertise to refine the solution. ● Successfully completed water filter tests in simulated environments at two wastewater treatment plants in Latvia, achieving 95% phosphorus removal efficiency. ● Advanced the scaled filter prototype and began validation activities with an industry technology partner in the Baltics. ● Finalized fertilizer product definition tests in collaboration with a Latvian institute, completed the first technical data sheet (version 1.0), and obtained initial performance data. ● Reached TRL 4 ("technology validated in laboratory environment") and advanced to TRL 5 activities, focusing on validation in industrially relevant environments. ● Started critical validation steps with industry partners, with plans for piloting and demonstrating the Letonite filter technology in Germany and the Netherlands by 2026. ● Developed strategic partnerships and laid the groundwork for demonstrating and piloting the technology in industrial settings. ● Planned pilot demonstrations for Q2 2025, with a focus on scaling and entering key European markets. <p>These achievements highlight the startup's commitment to addressing environmental challenges through innovation and collaboration, positioning its Letonite technology for impactful market entry in the near future.</p>
<p>Pinky Tech</p>	<p>This startup has made remarkable progress in both business and product development, achieving key milestones that position it for commercial success.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Successfully onboarded 5 early adopters (small businesses), converting 3 of them into paying customers. ● Secured a partnership agreement with one of the largest ISPs in the region, expanding market reach and credibility. ● Implemented the "Translation" feature on the platform, transforming technical descriptions of discovered vulnerabilities into business-oriented insights focused on risks and impact.

STARTUP NAME	KEY ACHIEVEMENTS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Launched the "Autoscan" feature, enabling users to schedule periodic scans and receive continuous alerts on security issues. ● Progressed with the development of the "Website Scan and Plugin" feature, which will enhance risk assessment capabilities and offer initial mitigation measures to users. <p>Currently at the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) stage, the startup is preparing for its first commercial release, showcasing significant advancements in addressing market needs. These achievements highlight the team's ability to balance technical innovation with strategic business growth.</p>
<p>The Newsroom</p>	<p>This startup has demonstrated exceptional progress in funding, market traction, and product performance, achieving significant milestones that underscore its growth potential.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Secured 6-digit grant funding, further supporting operations and development. ● Strengthened relationships with (predominantly female) angels and fund managers across Europe, laying the groundwork for potential equity funding in the second half of next year. ● Achieved a 4X increase in revenue since the programme's start, showcasing strong market acceptance and business scalability. ● Signed a major broadcaster in Portugal during the programme and onboarded another major broadcaster recently, highlighting its appeal to prominent clients. ● Focused on expanding market reach in the UK, which has been identified as the primary market for immediate growth opportunities. ● Enhanced platform capabilities, achieving a 5X increase in speed and an 80% improvement in accuracy. These upgrades have significantly improved customer satisfaction and shortened the sales cycle with prospects. ● Maintained a continuous improvement mindset, despite already having a market-ready, revenue-generating product. <p>These achievements reflect the startup's ability to balance financial growth, market expansion, and technological innovation, positioning it as a leader in its industry.</p>

9. FEEDBACK PROCESS

9.1 Overview of Feedback Collection Methods

Throughout the Acceleration programme, feedback was collected multiple times to gain a comprehensive understanding of its impact, value, and potential for growth among participating startups. The main goal was to gather as many insights as possible from various stakeholders involved in the programme.

The methods for collecting feedback included:

1. **Feedback from Lead Coaches on Startups:** Collected three times during the programme (Month 1, Month 4, Month 6) to assess startup progress and coaching effectiveness.
2. **Feedback from Startups on Lead Coaches:** Collected twice during the programme (Month 3 and Month 6) to evaluate the coaching experience and identify areas for improvement.
3. **Feedback on Acceleration Programme Part 1:** Gathered from startups to assess the effectiveness of the first part of the programme.
4. **Feedback on Acceleration Programme Part 2:** Collected to evaluate the second part of the programme.
5. **Feedback from Extra Mentors on Startups:** A total of 60 feedback results were collected to evaluate mentor effectiveness and startup performance.
6. **Feedback from Startups on Extra Mentoring Sessions:** A total of 60 feedback results were gathered to understand the impact of additional mentoring sessions.
7. **Feedback from Mentors on Startups after Mentor Day:** 16 feedback results were collected to assess the mentors' experiences and effectiveness.
8. **Feedback from Startups on Mentors after Mentor Day:** 13 feedback results were gathered to evaluate the effectiveness of mentors and their impact on the startups.

This comprehensive approach ensured that insights were gathered from all relevant parties, allowing for continuous improvement of the programme and its offerings.

9.2 Participant Feedback on Programme Effectiveness

Feedback to measure the programme's effectiveness was collected twice—once after Part 1 and again after Part 2. The main goal was to assess the programme from the startups' perspectives and identify any potential improvements where feasible. A review of the feedback revealed several highlights:

1. **Top Acceleration Programme:** Participants unanimously regarded this as the best startup Acceleration programme they had ever attended.
2. **Effective Communication:** Prompt and effective communication with programme managers was identified as a key factor in the programme's success.
3. **High Satisfaction Rating:** The programme received an average rating of 5 out of 5, indicating a high level of participant satisfaction.
4. **Positive Feedback:** Both Part 1 and Part 2 received overwhelmingly positive feedback, with participants appreciating all the activities included in the programme.
5. **Valuable Content:** The content of the programme was considered very useful, providing startups with essential knowledge and tools for their development.
6. **Community Building:** Peer-to-peer sessions played a crucial role in fostering a sense of community among participants. These sessions allowed startups to feel heard and share common challenges, strengthening their connections with one another.

9.3 Analysis of Mentor and Expert Feedback Data

We collected over 100 feedback forms from mentors and experts on startups and, upon analysis, identified several recurring suggestions. Common feedback included the need for clearer presentation of the startups' ideas, a more defined go-to-market strategy, and greater focus on business development. It was also noted that many products are still in the prototyping stage, and teams were advised to accelerate their progress and balance time spent on R&D. Despite these areas for improvement, none of the feedback questioned the value or innovation of the products. In fact, experts predict great success, provided that the correct steps are taken moving forward.

10. ANALYTICAL INSIGHTS

10.1 Success Factors for Women-Led Deep Tech Startups

The EmpoWOMEN programme has proven to be an invaluable resource for women-led deep tech startups, offering a blend of learning, networking, and practical support that has significantly contributed to their growth and success.

The programme helped founders develop both personally and professionally. As one participant noted, the programme allowed them as a female founder to not only transform their own vision but also to shape the future of their company. Participants expressed gratitude for the resources provided which offered practical

insights and helped develop teams, enhance leadership skills, and refine their company strategies. These resources were integral to addressing the challenges of leading a startup and growing as a founder.

All the startups emphasized the value of the programme's practical approach to learning. The emphasis on applying knowledge in real-time to their startup's specific challenges was particularly beneficial. For example, the opportunity to engage in meaningful learning while simultaneously applying new concepts to prototype development, business planning, and market engagement was highly motivating. This mix of knowledge acquisition and immediate application allowed startups to make tangible progress while learning the critical skills needed for success.

The programme created a strong network of like-minded founders, allowing participants to share experiences and insights with others who were at a similar stage in their journey. This peer support was invaluable, particularly for tackling unique challenges that startups face at early stages. The opportunity to connect with others navigating similar hurdles helped build a sense of community and motivation, creating an environment of mutual learning and support.

Participants noted the programme's focus on growth, learning, and practical outcomes. It was not just about acquiring theoretical knowledge, but about equipping startups with actionable strategies and tools that could be immediately implemented. This focus on results-driven learning, rather than unnecessary bureaucracy, allowed startups to concentrate on the most important aspects of their business development.

The programme also supported startups in refining their business strategies and preparing for future funding opportunities. For instance, provided assistance they received in preparing their pitch deck and developing a comprehensive funding strategy. This support, along with a clear understanding of how the investment process works, helped them build a stronger foundation for future fundraising.

Finally, the programme's grant support was highlighted as a key advantage. Many participants expressed that the financial assistance was the final touch, helping them to move forward with their operations and scale their startups.

The EmpoWOMEN programme provided these women-led startups with the resources, guidance, and network needed to scale their businesses, refine their strategies, and confidently prepare for future market entry and funding opportunities.

10.2 Barriers and Challenges Identified

Throughout the programme, startups encountered various barriers and challenges that impacted their progress, providing valuable insights for further development. Key challenges included technical hurdles, funding issues, market strategy adjustments, and operational constraints.

Several startups faced difficulties when moving from laboratory conditions to prototype development. For example, achieving the target accuracy under laboratory conditions didn't always translate to the desired outcomes in real-world prototypes. This required adjustments in design, including changes to reagents and prototypes to improve performance.

Securing additional funding was a significant challenge for some startups, particularly those in the medical and tech sectors. The need for ongoing financial support was compounded by the complexities of fundraising, which often involved fine-tuning strategies, automating data analysis, and engaging with potential investors or distributors.

Startups had to refine their business models based on customer feedback, which necessitated redesigning their products. Shifting from a purely B2C approach to a blended B2C and B2B2C model was one such adjustment.

Some startups struggled with balancing ambitious goals and key performance indicators (KPIs) against external factors, such as scheduling delays and client meetings. The development of prototypes, even in their first iteration, posed operational challenges, and navigating the complexities of product-market fit took longer than expected.

A few startups were in the middle of strategic pivots, which required revisiting their operational focus and market approach. Adjusting to the new direction proved challenging at times, especially when clashing schedules and external commitments made it difficult to engage fully in programme activities.

Identifying the right investors was another hurdle, especially for startups that were still early in their development stages. Geographic location, product stage, and industry-specific requirements all played a role in determining the best-fit investors, which posed additional challenges for some.

These challenges highlight the inherent complexities in building a startup, particularly in the deep-tech and med-tech sectors, and underscore the need for continued support and flexibility in addressing them.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

11.1 Strategic Recommendations for Future Programmes

To continue driving success for female-led deep tech startups, future acceleration programmes can focus on several strategic areas based on feedback and observed impacts from this six-month initiative:

7. **Tailored content aligned with maturity level:** Ensuring content aligns with the startup's maturity stage creates a stronger foundation for measurable progress. A modular approach, where content is segmented for early, mid, and late-stage startups, allows participants to engage with resources and

sessions that directly support their immediate goals. Early-stage startups, for instance, might benefit from content on foundational business strategies, ideation, and prototyping, while mid-stage startups could focus on product-market fit, scaling strategies, and establishing solid revenue models. Late-stage startups would gain more from investor readiness, scaling operations, and international expansion strategies. This structure optimizes the experience for each company, ensuring that they receive the right insights at the right time, enhancing participation value and accelerating their path to growth.

8. **Enhanced focus on investor readiness:** Since funding challenges are particularly acute for early-stage startups, especially those led by women, expanding investor readiness support is crucial. Providing sessions on building investor relationships, networking strategies, and preparing for fundraising pitches can empower participants to engage confidently with potential investors.
9. **Mentorship diversity and availability:** Access to a diverse mentor pool with deep expertise in both technology and industry-specific challenges is vital. It is recommended that future programmes increase mentor options, ensuring they include domain experts, seasoned entrepreneurs, and technical advisors who can provide insights tailored to deep tech.
10. **Community building and peer learning:** A strong community fosters peer-to-peer support, collaboration, and learning. Future programmes should emphasize activities that encourage networking and knowledge-sharing among participants, including peer feedback sessions and discussion forums.
11. **Comprehensive support for product development milestones:** Emphasizing support for reaching product development milestones—from prototyping to market launch—through tailored technical workshops and prototype feedback can help participants transition effectively from concept to product.
12. **Dedicated support for women entrepreneurs in male-dominated sectors:** Provide sessions focused on resilience-building, negotiation skills, and confidence in navigating male-dominated industries. Strategic content around building credibility and visibility as female leaders in tech could enhance participants' leadership journeys.
13. **Incorporating flexible KPIs and feedback loops:** Future programmes should maintain agility by regularly reviewing startups' progress and incorporating feedback-driven adjustments. This approach ensures that startups receive relevant guidance and that programme resources are aligned with their evolving needs.

14. **Ongoing Alumni network and post-programme support:** Establishing an active alumni network can extend the benefits of the programme beyond completion, offering continued mentorship, networking opportunities, and shared resources. Post-programme support such as pitch events and investor introductions would help maintain momentum and provide critical connections as participants enter the next phase of growth.

With the implementation of these strategic recommendations, our aim for future programmes is to amplify their impact, enabling more female-led deep tech startups to achieve sustainable growth, attract investment, and confidently scale their businesses in a competitive landscape.

11.2 Long-Term Strategies for Supporting Women-Led Deep Tech Startups

The journey of women-led deep tech startups is filled with unique challenges and opportunities that require tailored support and strategic long-term planning. This six-month Acceleration Programme has provided crucial resources and guidance, addressing not only the technical and business needs but also the distinct barriers that women entrepreneurs face within the deep tech landscape. By building on these insights, the following recommendations outline pathways for sustained growth, empowerment, and success for women founders in deep tech. Focusing on long-term strategies, we aim to foster a robust ecosystem that champions inclusivity, provides targeted resources, and supports the ongoing impact of women innovators.

1. **Funding accessibility:** Increasing funding access is crucial for women-led deep tech startups, especially in early stages. Expanding funding programmes that focus on female founders, creating dedicated venture capital funds, and building partnerships with investors committed to gender diversity can address the equity gap. Also, promoting mentorship between investors and founders offers both financial backing and strategic guidance.
2. **Expanding mentor networks:** A robust, diverse mentor network connects founders with advisors who understand both the tech landscape and unique challenges faced by women in deep tech. This can include experienced female tech leaders, advocates for gender equity, and specialists in core business functions like scaling and international market entry. Regular mentor interactions contribute to founders' confidence, skill-building, and access to industry insights.
3. **Creating safe and inclusive events:** Events should prioritize inclusivity and offer networking opportunities tailored for women in tech. Focused networking sessions, leadership workshops, and discussions on overcoming industry-specific gender challenges can foster an empowering environment where women-led startups can freely connect, share insights, and build alliances.

4. **Technical upskilling and leadership training:** Continuous education in technical areas and leadership skills, such as public speaking, negotiation, and team management, can position women founders for long-term success. Workshops on emerging technologies and certifications in technical fields equip founders with up-to-date expertise, while leadership programmes reinforce confidence and vision.
5. **Building community alliances:** Partnering with women-focused organizations, universities, and research institutions creates a support network for sustained growth. Collaboration with women-led initiatives and groups provides peer support, access to resources, and encourages solidarity, enabling women entrepreneurs to tackle challenges collaboratively and contribute to a growing community of empowered women in deep tech.
6. **Highlighting success stories:** Regularly showcasing achievements of female-led startups boosts visibility and provides inspiration for future female founders. Success stories serve as a powerful reminder of what women-led ventures can accomplish, encouraging a culture of inclusivity and representation across the tech ecosystem.

By addressing these core areas, future programmes can support women-led deep tech startups in building resilience, advancing innovation, and positioning themselves as key players in the global tech landscape.

12. CONCLUSIONS

12.1 Overall Impact of the Acceleration Programme

The impact of this programme on the women-led deep tech ecosystem is profound and far-reaching. Through the EmpoWOMEN initiative, many female founders have been inspired to continue developing their products, knowing that supportive programmes like this exist to assist them. Participants had the invaluable opportunity to connect with other female founders, sharing their journeys and receiving advice on how to succeed as women entrepreneurs.

Throughout the Acceleration Programme, it became evident that being among peers who faced similar challenges was one of the most powerful motivators, driving participants to work harder and remain committed to their goals. The sense of community fostered during the programme was highly valued by all participants.

Moreover, the programme provided opportunities to engage with female role models, business angels, and venture capitalists (VCs), equipping participants with the knowledge and confidence needed for fundraising. This exposure helped them understand precisely what investors are looking for, further strengthening their positions in the competitive landscape of deep tech

13. APPENDICES

13.1 List of Mentors and Coaches

Lead coaches

Table 10. Lead Coaches

Expert	Assigned startups	Origin of expert	Areas of expertise
Expert 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● GMZ Enerji ● GOTECH Antimicrobial ● P-Agro Minerals 	Ukraine	Product definition and positioning, product-market fit, early-stage investments.
Expert 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HUGUP 	Latvia	Marketing communications, branding, pitching, PR.
Expert 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Heilo ● Innosensus ● IQ BIOZOOM 	United Kingdom	Business development, design, branding, product-market fit.
Expert 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pinky Tech ● IPLEXMED 	Germany	Business development, marketing, growth hacking, and user acquisition.
Expert 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Astroteq.ai ● The Newsroom 	Tunisia	Software engineering and management, idea validation, product-market fit.

Table 11. Mentors & Experts

Expert	Assigned startups	Origin of expert	Areas of expertise
Acceleration Programme Lead	Welcome session, Peer to Peer sessions, Progress Day, Demo Day	Latvia	IT Project management, product and programme design.
Project manager	Q&A EmpoWOMEN programme	Latvia	Project management, pitching
Coach	Webinar and Q&A, SMART and SDG goal-setting	Ukraine	Product definition and positioning, product-market fit, early-stage investments.
Coach	Q&A "Problem Definition"	United States of America	Public speaking coach, pitch training, product definition and positioning

Expert	Assigned startups	Origin of expert	Areas of expertise
Coach	Q&A "MVP & Planning"	Tunisia	Software engineering and management, idea validation, product-market fit.
Coach	Webinar "Pitching"	Latvia	Marketing communications, branding, pitching, PR.
Coach	Q&A "Sales"	Ukraine	IT Business Development, Product Development, and Sales.
Coach	Q&A "Fundraising"	Ukraine	Fundraising, Business Development, Investor Relations.
Coach	Q&A "Legal"	Estonia	Intellectual Property, GDPR, legal matters.

Table 12. Coaches of Part 2

Expert	Assigned startups	Origin of expert	Areas of expertise
Coach/Investor	Understanding the Needs and requirements of deep tech Investors	Romania/Germany	Angel Investor VC Investor Deeptech expert and recognised Author and international speaker on deeptech.
Coach/Investor	How to develop an effective deeptech investment proposal	France and Spain	Angel Investor and expert in STEM. Founder of WA4STEM investing in women in STEM
Coach/Investor	Understanding your financial projections and Investment needs	Slovakia	Angel Investor; Founder of LUMUS women Angel investment group in CE; Exited entrepreneur
Coach/Investor	How to present your financial investment proposal to investors and what Angels and VC investors require	France and Belgium	Angel Investor; VC Investor; Founder of National Angel Network of Belgium; Co-Founder of two scale up VC Funds
Coach/Investor	How to develop an effective and comprehensive Toolkit to meet the requirements of investors and prepare for direct engagement with investors	Romania and France	Experienced Investor in Technology and Innovation.Co-Founder of Women In technology and Women in technology Angels

Expert	Assigned startups	Origin of expert	Areas of expertise
Coach/Investor	Making a winning pitch to investors practical examples and points of consideration as a women deeptech entrepreneur.	Ireland	Exited tech Entrepreneur; Experienced Woman Investor; Co-Founder of Women Awaken Hub; Co-Founder of Awaken Women Angels 100% investments in women founders
Coach/Investor	Developing your skills in effectively negotiating with investors during and post pitch	Estonia and UK	Experienced tech Entrepreneur; Angel investor; Co-Founder of Sie Ventures empowering women to access investment and direct investments
Coach/Investor	In depth understanding of how to prepare for and engage in the due diligence process and what investors look for.	Italy	Experienced VC Fund Manager and Angel Investor with specific focus on Deeptech and Innovation;
Coach/Investor	How to value your business for investment purposes and how to understand the approach that investors and the methodologies that can be applied	France	Experienced Angel and Vc Investor . Exited entrepreneur sand deal leader in Femmes Business Angels
Coach/Investor	How to proceed through Due Diligence and implications for deeptech investor requirements and decision-making	Netherlands	Experienced Deeptech Angel investor and expert in BioScience
Coach/Investor	Understanding the Requirements and process for the Termsheet and achieving a successful outcome	France	Experienced Angela nd VC Investor in Technology and Innovation; Founder of WINEquity
Coach/Investor	Understanding the legal contractual process and key legal documentation to structure the deal	Romania	Lawyer Legal Expert and Legal Counsel; Experienced Angel investor and co-Founder of Women in technology

13.2 Mentor Profiles and Expertise

The female-led deep tech startups participating in the Acceleration Programme had access to an extensive network of mentors and industry experts, providing a comprehensive foundation of knowledge and practical

insights across critical areas of startup growth. These experts offered guidance on a wide range of topics essential to building a successful deep tech company, including:

- **Strategic Business Growth:** Experts in areas such as B2B sales, business development, scaling, and go-to-market strategies provided startups with the tools and frameworks needed to enter markets effectively and scale their operations.
- **Sector-Specific Insights:** With mentors specializing in fields such as IoT, cybersecurity, digital health, health tech, Agtech, startups received valuable sector-specific guidance that enabled them to navigate the technical and regulatory complexities unique to their industry.
- **Product and Team Development:** Mentors in product management, product design, team dynamics, leadership, and ideal customer persona helped founders refine their products, develop strong team structures, and focus on their customers' needs.
- **Finance and Fundraising:** With access to finance and fundraising mentors, startups gained critical knowledge on securing investments, financial planning, and understanding their financial pathways for growth.
- **Marketing and Branding:** Guidance on branding, digital marketing, pitching, and ideal customer validation helped startups enhance their market presence and build a strong brand foundation.

Through this diverse mentorship network, startups were able to tackle challenges with the support of specialized guidance, positioning them for long-term success.

13.3 Startup Attendance Rate

The startup attendance rate was one of the key performance indicators (KPI) of the project, and maintaining a minimum attendance of 75% was required for startups to qualify for the full grant of €45,000. Attendance was measured by the number of live sessions each startup participated in.

For Part 1 of the programme, attendance was tracked using the Airtable tool, where all startups had access to the recorded data. In Part 2, due to the different content and management approach, attendance was monitored via Google Spreadsheet. This system ensured transparency and allowed startups to track their progress toward meeting this essential KPI.

Table 13. Attendance Rate

STARTUP NAME	PART 1 ATTENDANCE RATE (%)	PART 2 ATTENDANCE RATE (%)	OVERALL ATTENDANCE RATE (%)
Astroteq.ai	95.65%	93.30%	94.73%

STARTUP NAME	PART 1 ATTENDANCE RATE (%)	PART 2 ATTENDANCE RATE (%)	OVERALL ATTENDANCE RATE (%)
GMZ Enerji	100%	100%	100%
GOTECH Antimicrobial	100%	100%	100%
Heilo sp. z o.o.	95.65%	86.66%	92.10%
HUGUP	95.65%	100%	97.36%
Innosensus, JSC	100%	100%	100%
IPLEXMED	100%	100%	100%
IQ BIOZOOM	95.65%	93.30%	94.73%
P-Agro Minerals	86.95%	100%	92.10%
Pinky Tech	100%	100%	100%
The Newsroom	91.30%	93.30%	92.10%

13.4 Acceleration Programme End

FIGURE. 7 EmpoWomen Demoday

Top 3 startups who received the monetary prizes:

1st place Astroteq.ai; 15 000 EUR

2nd place IPLEXMED; 11 500 EUR

2nd place GOTECH Antimicrobial 6 000 EUR

FIGURE. 8 EmpoWomen Demoday Award Ceremony

13.5 OC#1 Selected Startups

13.5.1 ASTROTEQ.AI

Startup Name	Astrotectonic Spolka z ograniczona odpowiedzialnoscia
Country	POLAND
PIC Number	888086411
Website	https://astroteq.ai/

Astroteq.ai offers an AI-driven earthquake forecasting system, providing alerts 14, 3, and 1 day(s) prior to earthquakes, unlike traditional last-minute warnings. It integrates hardware and software to predict earthquakes by analyzing various data channels for enhanced accuracy. This innovation empowers governments, businesses, and insurers to proactively safeguard lives and assets. This paradigm shift grants critical preparation time, allowing authorities to activate emergency protocols, evacuate vulnerable areas, and secure critical infrastructure. Businesses and insurers, armed with this foresight, can take proactive measures to protect lives and valuable assets. The heart of AstroTeq.ai lies in its continuous research and development. Scientists, engineers, and data analysts.

13.5.2 GMZ ENERJİ SİSTEMLERİ SANAYİ VE TİCARET LIMITED SİRKETİ

Startup Name	GMZ Enerji Sistemleri Sanayi ve Ticaret Limited Sirketi
Country	TÜRKİYE
PIC Number	879115948
Website	https://gmzenerji.com/en/

As GMZ Enerji, we develop innovative solutions for electrolyzer and fuel cell systems, which are hydrogen energy technologies. The heart of both systems is membranes. These membranes contain high technology and have high added value. Although high cost is one of the biggest problems in commercial membranes prepared by normal casting method, performance, strength and production sustainability are the features

that need to be improved. The nanofiber membranes we developed with machine learning and artificial intelligence-based performance optimization solutions and produced using the electrospinning method have up to 10 times higher performance and lower costs. Additionally, their negative environmental effects are minimized due to their non-fluorinated structure. Electrospinning device subcomponents that enable the production of nanofiber membranes with desired properties are also among our products.

13.5.3 GO ANTIMICROBIAL TECHNOLOGIES, LDA

Startup Name	GO Antimicrobial Technologies, Lda
Country	PORTUGAL
PIC Number	878699818
Website	http://www.gotechantimicrobial.com/

GOTECH Antimicrobial is a Portuguese MedTech startup founded by 2 women, and develops advanced and disruptive disinfection systems to solve medical device-related infection. Given the severe impact on society (15% patient mortality rate) and healthcare systems’ economy (~37k€/infection in US), we are addressing hemodialysis catheter-related infections (CRIs) with our first product, the GOcap®: a light-activated graphene-based cap for catheter disinfection. Unlike other solutions, GOcap® reusability and long-term antimicrobial action will prevent infection, reduce costs, avoid disposal of millions of plastic caps, extend catheters lifespan, without contributing to antibiotic resistance, while improving patients’ quality of life. Core activities focus on rolling-out our flagship product from R&D and IP protection to market assessment and regulatory affairs, building a product pipeline, while providing R&D services/consultancy throughout biomaterials and medical devices life cycle.

13.5.4 HUGUP SP. Z O.O.

Startup Name	HUGUP SP. Z O.O.
Country	POLAND

PIC Number	889155448
Website	https://www.hugup.com/

HUGUP is a deep tech startup revolutionizing pregnancy wellness with its advanced support wear, addressing the widespread yet underserved issue of lumbopelvic pain affecting two-thirds of pregnant women. By merging cutting-edge scientific research in orthopaedics, physiotherapy, and biomechanics with innovative, flexible materials, HUGUP has developed a unique, holistic support garment. Designed for daily, comfortable wear, it distributes belly weight evenly, improving posture and alleviating pain. Pre-launch testing validated HUGUP's effectiveness over competitors, demonstrating its potential to significantly improve pregnant individuals' quality of life. Aiming for a profound societal impact, HUGUP combines deep tech innovation with practical application, ensuring safety, comfort, and empowerment for expectant mothers.

13.5.5 HEILO SP. Z O.O.

Startup Name	Heilo sp. z o.o.
Country	POLAND
PIC Number	883190239
Website	https://heilo.eu/en/

Heilo, an impact startup, addresses infant exposure to air pollution while commuting with its advanced baby pram and stroller cover. The integrated air purifying system filters pollutants, ensuring a safe environment. Developed collaboratively with scientists, engineers, physicians and parents Heilo's solution combines electronic air purification and smart sensor technology, capturing 95% of contaminants with minimal noise. The multifunctional design fits 95% of prams, offering comprehensive protection. Intellectual property protection includes an utility model patent for air-cleaning modules and EU Industrial Design and Trademark protection. Heilo aligns with trends in children's health and environmental concerns. WHO statistics highlight global child exposure to polluted air (93% of children in the world breathe polluted air!). The startup leverages the growing baby tech industry and increased health consciousness.

13.5.6 IPLEXMED, LDA

IPLEXMED

Startup Name	IPLEXMED, Lda
Country	PORTUGAL
PIC Number	889428018
Website	http://www.iplexmed.com/

IPLEXMED's solution, NEXAGUARD, delivers unprecedented detection of multiple infectious agents and antimicrobial resistance from a non-invasive sample, at the point-of-care (ER) and at-home, in a fast, single run. This is crucial for chronic respiratory diseases patients (CRDs), 1 Bn sufferers with 3 Mn premature deaths/y due to respiratory infections, often antimicrobial resistant. Current tools for infectious agents detection are timely, expensive and not suitable for at-home. NEXAGUARD provides lab-grade fast personalized diagnostic results on-site, reducing diagnosis time from 2-7 days to 20min, supporting decentralized, timely personalized diagnostics and saving 40% on healthcare costs on unnecessary hospitalizations and/or drug prescriptions. We pave the way for ER/at-home lab-grade diagnosis contributing to decrease the 112 Mn disability-adjusted life years caused by CRDs. IPLEXMED's technology will favor entrance in a 12 Bn market by 2025, and will also target other markets.

13.5.7 IQ BIOZOOM SP. Z O.O.

IQ Biozoom

Startup Name	IQ Biozoom sp. z o.o.
Country	POLAND
PIC Number	878616495
Website	https://iqbiozoom.com/

IQ Biozoom is a pioneering company dedicated to improving the management of personal health through non-invasive, pain-free diagnostic home tests. They focus on the development of biosensing technology for

real-time diagnostic tests, with their flagship product being a revolutionary medical device designed for non-invasive and pain-free glucose, cortisol and lactate monitoring. IQ BioZoom tests are instantaneous, precise (laboratory quality in home conditions), non-invasive (without the need for puncturing/drawing blood), and the device is universal (one analyzer allows for the measurement of many biomarkers), reusable, while production costs are low. The advantages of the IQ BioZoom device and tests stem from the application of new technology owned by the Company. Founded in Poland, the company has gained international attention, including TOP 10 of the EIT Health InnoStars Awards and being selected as Hello Tomorrow Deep Tech Pioneers in 2023.

13.5.8 INNOSENSUS

INNOSENSUS

Startup Name	Innosensus
Country	LITHUANIA
PIC Number	884862907
Website	https://www.innosensus.com/

It is estimated that 1 of 7 Europeans do not tolerate gluten. These gluten intolerant people day by day meets with unpleasant symptoms, such as indigestion, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, skin rashes, tooth erosion, fatigue, joint pain, etc., because even the smallest amount of gluten causes the disease to get worse. Problem: Today there is no rapid and effective way to detect the presence of gluten in the food. Solution: Innosensus is creating a personal gluten biosensor, which quickly detects the presence of gluten in the food, and helps to prevent unpleasant symptoms for gluten intolerant people & with celiace disease. Gluten indicator would open the possibility for our target group to monitor of gluten daily: to have lunch or dinner in the public places, to enjoy food with maximum protection for themselves & feel less stress when eating outside the home. Innosensus gluten biosensor will be 10 times faster than other existing methods to test food for gluten

13.5.9 P-AGRO MINERALS

Startup Name	P-Agro Minerals
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Country	LATVIA
PIC Number	878817285
Website	https://www.linkedin.com/company/p-agro-minerals

P-Agro Minerals manufactures an environmentally friendly innovative material called Letonite, specifically designed to facilitate polluting nutrient - phosphorus (P) removal from wastewater and after using recovered P as fertiliser. P-Agro offers two products in the market - Letonite wastewater filter for nutrient recovery and Letonite fertiliser. P-Agro Minerals tackle the pressing water treatment industry issue to purify municipal and industrial wastewaters from P to regulatory standards. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are actively seeking solutions that can be integrated into their existing treatment processes. P-Agro Minerals is in EIT RawMaterials Accelerator stage 2-3, which ensures to finalise the Letonite wastewater filter technology validation activities in WWTP and prepare for demonstration activity in year 2025, a phase that includes active participation from industry stakeholders and prospective customers.

13.5.10 PINKY TECH SRL

Startup Name	Pinky Tech SRL
Country	MOLDOVA
PIC Number	877340751
Website	http://www.pinkytech.com/

Over 50% of cyberattacks target SMEs, either directly or through Supply Chain Attacks, while these family-owned business have no knowledge, no awareness of potential threats. Each day, these smaller companies experience financial losses, damage to their reputation, and legal battles as a result of these attacks, with estimated losses per one attack – EUR 35'000. Pinky CyberSafe® is a SaaS Platform tailored specifically to fit SMEs requirements: lack of knowledge in cybersecurity, limited resources and need for robust cybersecurity. Pinky® aims to become one-stop AI-driven solution that will encompass tools and procedures that will shield these unprotected customers from potential threats while also increasing their cybersecurity awareness. We make cybersecurity accessible for SMEs due to our streamlined UI/UX design that simplifies the process and ML algorithms that make it smart covering SMEs need for skilled IT security professionals.

13.5.11 TÍTULO ALTERNATIVO, LDA

Startup Name	TÍTULO ALTERNATIVO, LDA
Country	PORTUGAL
PIC Number	890276962
Website	https://www.thenewsroom.ai/

The Newsroom addresses the issues of misinformation and filter bubbles in news consumption and production. It consists of an AI-powered technology that analyzes thousands of news articles daily, identifies and summarizes consensus and different perspectives from various sources in multiple languages. It has been trained for three years on over 4 million news articles, in 6 languages. The platform offers a mobile app for readers, guiding them from common ground to diverse viewpoints, and a News AI co-pilot for journalists to assist in research, contextualization, and fact-checking. This comprehensive approach aims to enhance the quality and balance of both news production and consumption.